

ISic3453

Fragmentary epitaph

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Arianna Cinquatti,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2014.10.30 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

Territory of Mineo, probably contrada Favarotta (37.307741,
14.710805)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini, inventory 5198

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 38 cm

Width 60 cm

Depth 10 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 90 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not measured mm

Text

1. [---]ανεικη
2. χᾶρῃ

Apparatus

Translation (en)

[---?]aneike, farewell!

Commentary

Note that there is a second separate text of Phronime engraved on the obverse of this stone (ISic 3452 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4532>]).

Digital identifiers:

TM 644929

EDCS 70900743

Bibliography

Cordano, F. 2014. Materiale vecchio e nuovo dalla Sicilia orientale. In Alfieri Tonini, T., Struffolino, S.(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica*. Trento. pp. 105-111. At 109 no.10b

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